

Table S1: Abundance of charcoal with different morphologies across different geomorphic regimes of Yamuna sub-basin

Tributaries	Morphology (%)			
	Leaves	Wood/herbaceous	Roots	Cones/needles
<i>Upland region</i>	20	75	n/a	5
<i>Lowland region</i>	10	80	10	n/a
<i>Lowland_Peninsular region</i>	20	76	4	n/a